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President-Elect Trump Appoints FDA and NIH Directors: President-elect Trump has chosen [John Hopkins' Dr. Martin Makery](#) to head the FDA and [Stanford's Dr. Jay Bhattacharya](#) to lead the NIH. Makery has been critical of [the Orphan Drug Act](#) pathway for rare disease treatments, arguing that it provides incentives for drugmakers to game the regulatory system for profit, as well as vaccine and mask mandates during the COVID-19 pandemic. Bhattacharya has likewise been openly critical of COVID-19 health measures, co-authoring the [Great Barrington Declaration](#) in 2020 calling for the end of lockdowns. Coupled with [Robert F Kennedy Jr.'s appointment as Health Secretary](#), the incoming Trump administration has positioned itself at odds with pharmaceutical companies.

[PREVAIL Act Narrowly Moves Forward Despite Concerns About Drug Pricing Impact:](#) The US Senate's Judiciary Committee narrowly passed the [Promoting and Respecting Economically Vital American Innovation Leadership \(PREVAIL\) Act](#), which aims to reform the Patent Trial and Appeal Board (PTAB), focusing on limiting multiple patent challenges and requiring standing for PTAB challengers, such as evidence of being sued for infringement. Critics worry the Act restricts access for patient advocacy groups and generic drug manufacturers to challenge patents, potentially keeping drug prices high. The passage of the Act into law is highly unlikely, as it would need to pass a full Senate and House floor vote and be signed by outgoing President Biden before the 119th Congress begins in January.

[EQBMED launches trial sites tool to assess performance and boost diversity:](#) The Equitable Breakthroughs in Medicine Development (EQBMED) initiative introduced the Site Maturity Assessment Model, a tool designed to help clinical trial sites evaluate their capacity for conducting diverse and inclusive trials. The model aims to enhance health equity by combining community engagement with research operations, which are components of clinical trials that are often siloed from one another.

[Canadian Intellectual Property Office \(CIPO\) Releases 2024 Report:](#) The CIPO 2024 IP Canada Report highlights that patent filings in Canada fell by 6% in 2023, marking the end of the filing rebound that followed COVID-19. The vast majority (88%) of applications received in 2023 originated from non-resident applicants, highlighting Canada's continued presence as a destination market.